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How Teacher–Student Relationships Influence High School Grading

Amariah Covington
Elizabeth Trepanier

Lake Brantley High School, Altamonte Springs, Florida, USA
Seminole State College, Altamonte Springs, Florida, USA

These authors contributed equally to this work.

41
42 **Key Words:**
43 Relationships
44 Grading
45 Mastery
46 Bias
47 Engagement

48
49 **Abstract:**

50 This study examines whether positive teacher-student relationships influence how high school teachers
51 grade their students. The project investigates whether rapport, engagement, and behavior affect teachers'
52 interpretations of student work and whether grades reflect academic mastery or familiarity. The findings
53 aim to clarify how relational dynamics shape grading practices in real classroom settings.

54
55 **Introduction:**

56 Grades are often treated as objective indicators of academic mastery, yet classroom evaluation is
57 shaped by far more than content recollection. A large body of research shows that teacher-student
58 relationships influence students' engagement, motivation, and achievement. Longitudinal studies from
59 Wentzel (1998) and Ryan et al. (1994) found that students who feel connected to their teachers show
60 higher motivation and persistence in their studies. While other works, such as studies from Hamre &
61 Pianta (2001) and Ladd et al. (1999), emphasized that early positive relationships can anticipate later
62 academic success for individuals. Finally, meta-analytic findings from Roorda et al. (2011) and Göktas &
63 Kaya (2023) found findings that further confirm that warm and responsive teacher-student relationships
64 are correlated with improved academic performance across grade levels K-12. Together, these studies
65 serve as the starting point of our research through their suggestion that relational dynamics are deeply
66 intertwined with how students behave and perform in their classrooms.

67 Although relationships clearly matter for learning, far less is known about how they influence
68 grading. Several studies suggest that teachers may interpret student work differently depending on their
69 perceptions of the student. For example, Gershenson (2016) researched teacher expectations, and his
70 research proved teacher sometimes judge the work of well-liked or highly engaged students more
71 favorably. Despite the fact that the academic quality is similar.
72 Other researchers, such as Ready and Wright (2011) and Ready (2013), found that teachers tend to give
73 credit to students who display effort, are excited about learning or have a good connection with them.
74 This raises the question if grades truly show the academic mastery of a student or if they are also based on
75 how the teacher knows the student, how much the student participates in class and how the teacher feels
76 about the student.

77 If teachers' perceptions influence how they interpret ambiguous or subjective work, then grades may
78 partially reflect the relationships rather than performance.

79 To combat prejudicial grading, attempts to standardize grading through rubrics and present
80 criteria have been made. However, these attempts have not fully eliminated subjectivity. Scholars, such as
81 Sadler (2009) and Tierney & Simon (2004), have debated in their publications that even well-designed
82 rubrics contain inherent indeterminacy, which thus leaves room for interpretation on open-ended
83 assignments. This enforces that grading is not purely objective and perhaps is influenced by relational and
84 contextual forces.

85 The main goal of our study was to examine how much positive relationships between teachers
86 and students affect the grades that teachers give in high school classes. This could lead to questions about
87 whether grading is fair, accurate and what it really means to achieve something in school. This was
88 addressed by the research question pushing forward this work: To what extent do positive teacher-student
89 relationships lead to more favorable grading outcomes? That led to the later study of teachers would
90 report that rapport, engagement and behavior make it easier to award partial credit, interpret unclear
91 answers positively and offer end-of-term leniency. If supported, this would insinuate that grades may
92 reflect relational dynamics as much as academic mastery. This would raise questions about fairness,
93 accuracy, and the meaning of achievement in school settings for later studies. We hypothesized that
94 although teacher-student relationships are known to influence motivation and achievement within
95 students, less is understood about how these relationships really shape teacher's grading decisions.
96 Therefore, this study investigates whether positive rapport, engagement, and a student's behavior could
97 lead to more favorable grading outcomes in high school classrooms.

98 99 **Results:**

100 This study used a 10-questions survey to find out whether positive teacher-student relationships
101 were influenced in grading decisions made by the teacher. The first five questions used Likert-scale items,
102 and the last five questions were open-ended. In total, 17 teachers completed the survey. Below, each
103 individual question is presented, along with its purpose, how it was measured, and what the results
104 showed.

105 The first question asked whether high levels of student engagements would make it easier for
106 teachers to give partial credit on subjective graded assignments. This question was asked for the purpose
107 of observing if "trying hard" could potentially influence grading. Most surveyed teachers agreed with this
108 question, with 58.8% selecting "agree", and 29.4% selected "Strongly agree". What must be noted is no
109 teacher selected "strongly disagree" or "no effect" (Figure 1). Therefore, this implies that teachers
110 generally do find it easier to justify partial credit when a student is clearly trying (in the teacher's point of
111 view)), even if the answer is not fully correct.

112 The second question asked whether a strong rapport helps teachers understand a student's
113 academic goal when an answer is unclear on an assignment. These questions tested whether relationships
114 between teachers and students could potentially influence how teachers interpret objectively, ambiguous
115 work. A majority of surveyed teachers agreed (43.8%) or strongly agreed (18.8%), however on the other
116 hand, smaller group selected the options of "Neutral", "Disagree", or "Strongly disagree" (figure 2). This
117 goes to prove that rapport can shape how teachers read student work, especially when the answer is not
118 straightforward and is left to interpretation.

119 The third question looked into whether participation and/or enthusiasm affect participation grades
120 compared to quiet or introverted students with similar academic output. Because the survey included
121 teacher from a wide range of subjects, such as math, science, English, social studies, and electives, the
122 expectation was for this question to vary the most. Consequently, this question produced mixed
123 responses. 23.5% agreed, 23.5% strongly agreed, 23.5% disagreed, and 11.8% strongly disagreed. The
124 rest of the participants selected "Neutral" or "No Effect" (Figure 3). This mix of results is logical
125 considering different subjects rely on student participation in a multitude of different ways. For example,
126 English based subjects may grade discussions more heavily on subjective performance. While on the
127 other hand, math-based subjects may focus more on accuracy and problem solving, thus offering more

128 objectivity. Overall, the mixed results show that participation grading is often highly teacher and student
129 dependent, but not a universal practice.

130 The fourth question asked whether teachers are more likely to offer extra credit or a grace period
131 to turn in later assignments to students who consistently work hard/ stay positive from a teacher's
132 perspective. The majority of surveyed teachers agreed, with 52.9% clicking agree, and 17.6% clicking
133 strongly agree (Figure 4). This implies that effort and attitude can absolutely influence end-of-term
134 decisions, even when the teachers believe they are acting in a completely objective manner.

135 The fifth question asked if teachers struggle to separate behavior from grading subjective work,
136 such as essays or projects. The results were 58.8% of surveyed teaches disagreeing, but an important
137 group (29.4%) agreed with this question (Figure 5). So, while many teachers truly do believe they are
138 acting from an objective perspective, others do admit that behavior and attitude can sneak into grading.
139 Thus, reinstating that other teacher may not be aware of their bias and believe they are being objective, or
140 operate from a biased perspective and accept that.

141 Furthermore, when moving to the open-ended questions, they provided more depth than the
142 Likert-scale ones. When teachers explained the difference between academic mastery and effort, almost
143 all of them stated that mastery is what a student can show on assessments. However, effort would be the
144 day-to-day behavior, attitude and engagement displayed in class. It must be stated that several teachers
145 pointed out that a student can be engaged in class yet not fully understand the content; or vice versa.

146 Teachers also shared the strategies they used to remain objective while they grade their
147 assignments. For example, some teachers rely on anonymous grading, detailed rubrics, answer keys,
148 grading without looking at names, as well as automated scoring for multiple choice tests which were more
149 popular for math-based subjects. A few of the surveyed teachers admitted that it is difficult to not have
150 expectations for certain students, especially high performers, however the participants stated that they
151 attempt to combat this by actively checking themselves.

152 Moreover, when asked whether a positive attitude can influence how teachers perceive mastery,
153 once again, the responses were mixed. A few teachers stated that the attitude of a student is completely
154 unrelated to how they would conduct grading, but on the other hand, other teachers admitted that a
155 respectful or enthusiastic student can form a positive impression on a teacher that may perhaps influence
156 how their work is interpreted. Lastly, some teachers provided personal stories where a student's attitude
157 made them more willing to offer help or second chances on an assignment.

158 Lastly, teachers discussed systemic pressures on students on how they might impact a student
159 grade on an assignment. While some stated they feel systemic pressures on students have no effect on
160 grading an assignment, others mentioned parental pressures, school culture about retakes of an
161 assignment and later work, and administrative policies that demand leniency. Furthermore, a few teachers
162 said that parents who advocate aggressively for their child more often end up receiving more attention,
163 which can indirectly affect grading opportunities.

164 Ultimately, the results display a want of teachers to remain objective, but through their
165 relationships teachers form with students, and the effort and outside pressures teachers observe in their
166 students, it plays a role in their grades. Thus, these results imply that a positive rapport and engagement in
167 class can influence how teachers interpret student work, especially when answers remain foggy or
168 assignments are subjective.

169
170 **Discussion:**

171 The results of this study show that while teachers attempt to grade based on a student's mastery
172 of a subject, relationships, effort, and outside pressures ultimately influence how grading decisions are
173 made. Across the five Likert-scale questions and the other five open-ended responses, the pattern that
174 human judgement is never fully separated from the relationships teachers build with students became
175 more obvious.

176 One of the clearest findings came from the first question. This was where most teachers agreed
177 that high student engagement would make it easier to provide partial credit to a student. Meaning, visible
178 effort plays a crucial role in how teachers perceive a student's work, especially on assignments that are
179 not strictly right or wrong. Moreover, the second questions provided a similar trend, with most teachers
180 answering that a strong rapport aids them in understanding a student's academic intent when an answer is
181 unclear. When both of these results are compared, they display that relationships ultimately shape how
182 teachers read and interpret student work, even despite their attempts to remain neutral.

183 Through this, the third question that produced the most mixed responses. This logically flows
184 because the survey included teachers from a wide range of subjects, including math, science, English and
185 social studies. Participation in each of those subjects will look different when compared to another. So, it
186 is not surprising that teachers disagreed on whether enthusiasm with correlate with higher participation
187 grade. Keep note that the diverse responses are important when interpreting the results, because subject-
188 area norms can influence how much behavior or engagement naturally become part of grading.

189 The fourth question provided insight to when teachers are more lightly to offer grace or extra
190 credit when a student is actively involved in the class or consistently works hard while maintaining a
191 positive attitude. This does not necessarily mean teachers are biased. It may reflect a belief that effort
192 deserves recognition, but it does not show that end-of-term decisions are not always based on a student's
193 mastery of a subject alone. Additionally, the fifth question revealed that for many teachers, separation is
194 difficult from a student's behavior and their work. While other surveyed teachers believe they can
195 separate the two.

196 The open-ended questions helped explain why these patterns exist. Teachers consistently
197 described academic mastery as what a student can do on assessments, while effort only shows daily
198 behavior and attitude. Many teachers said that their rapport with a student's aids them in understanding
199 why a student might be struggling, thus influencing how they respond, such as offering support,
200 flexibility or a second chance. One teacher even emailed me separately to say, "Teachers are human like
201 everyone else and can have favorites, but I think you can still grade fairly." Additionally, some teachers
202 mentioned that having a favorite can sometimes raise expectation, with one teacher stating they graded
203 their own children "far more strictly than their peers." Thus, this only goes to show the idea that
204 relationships do not make teachers closely more lenient, but also they sometimes make teachers tougher.

205 There are several limitations to this study. First and foremost, the sample size was small (17
206 teachers), and the subject-area distribution was uneven. Because the teachers from different subjects
207 grade differently, this perhaps have influenced the results, especially for questions about participation and
208 subjective grading. Secondly, the results relied on a self-report, which means teachers may answer based
209 on how they believe they grade, rather than how they actually grade in their practice. Thirdly, the survey
210 did not measure actual grading behavior. The survey only demonstrated the teacher's perception of their
211 own grading. These limitations go to show that while the results do show a trend, they can not be
212 generalized o all teachers or all schools.

213 Despite these limitations, the findings are still meaningful. They show that teacher-student
214 relationships, student effort, and external pressures all play a role in grading decisions even while teachers

215 try to remain objective. This matters because so often in brick-and-mortar school systems, grades are
216 often treated as a direct measure of mastery, when in reality they may reflect a combination of mastery,
217 and teacher-student rapport.

218 Future research could build on this study in many helpful ways. Such as a larger sample size
219 would help determine whether these patterns hold more broadly. Observational studies or analysis of
220 anonymized student assignments could potentially compare teachers stated beliefs with their actually
221 grading practices. Additionally, it would be useful to explore how grading varies by subject area, since
222 participation and subjectivity look different in math, English, and science classes. Finally, future studies
223 could examine whether training in a bias-aware grading practice changes how a teacher would evaluate
224 subjective work.

225 Ultimately, this study implies that while teachers value fairness and objectivity, relationships and
226 effort still influence grading in many ways. Understanding these types of dynamics can aid schools to
227 create grading systems that are more transparent and consistent for a student's mastery and growth.
228

229 **Materials and Methods:**

230 This study used an anonymous online survey to measure teacher's perceptions of how teacher-
231 student relationships impact their grading. A ten-question survey was created using Google Forms, which
232 included five Likert-scale items and five open-ended questions. The Likert-scale items used a six-option
233 response format in the specific order: "Strongly disagree", "Disagree", "Neutral", "Agree", "Strongly
234 Agree", and "No effect". This quantified the surveyed teacher's attitudes toward effort, rapport and their
235 own grading practices. Then five open ended questions followed to help collect more detailed
236 explanations of how teachers define mastery, how they manage bias, and then how they interpret their
237 students' struggles.

238 To collect responses, 100 teachers across five public high schools in Seminole County, Florida
239 were emailed the survey link in a standardized email. The teachers represented multiple subject areas
240 which included math, science, English, social studies, and elective courses. The participation of these
241 teachers was voluntary, and no identifying information was collected. In the standardized email sent to
242 each of the 100 teachers and in the description above the questions of the survey, the teachers were
243 informed that the survey was anonymous and that their responses would be used for research on grading
244 perceptions. A few teachers responded to the standardized email which provided additional evidence
245 regarding their grading practices; these comments were included in the discussion and results.

246 The survey remained open for one week, during which 17 teachers completed it. Google forms
247 automatically recorded and organized the responses. The quantitative result from the Likert-scale
248 questions were transformed into percentages and displayed using the built-in pie chart generator in
249 Google Forms. The qualitative responses were analyzed in a standardized approach. In which, all of the
250 open-ended answers were read individually, identified the recurring points, and grouped them into a
251 broader theme related to either master, rapport or eternal pressure.

252 Because this study relied heavily on self-reported perceptions rather than experimental
253 manipulation, no control group was used. Anonymity served as the main method for reducing potential
254 social desirability bias that could occur. All the procedures invited minimal risk and used only
255 anonymous adult response; therefore, no extra ethical review was required.
256

257 **Conclusion:**

258 Overall, this study is a testament that grading is not a robotic, mechanical process, but a human
259 process. Even when teachers work hard to remain objective, their decisions are shaped but the
260 relationships they build, effort they see and the expectation placed on them by their school environment.
261 What stood out the most in this study, is not that the teachers were biased, but instead that they are
262 conscious of the tension between fairness and empathy. Of which, many actively create systems to protect
263 their grading from their own personal influence.

264 On the same side of that coin, the results crystalize that effort, rapport and context still matter.
265 These factors do not replace a student's mastery, but they do shape how teachers interpret a student's
266 work. It is that nuance that is vital to understanding the importance of this whole study. It means that
267 grades are not restricted to what their definition of a reflection of academic mastery is but also is a
268 reflection of the environment in which they learn.

269 Moreover, these findings matter beyond the high school classroom. These grades become a part
270 of a student's transcript, which is often the first thing colleges look at. If effort, rapport or simply teacher
271 expectations subtly, but surely influence their grades, then these small factors build over time and can
272 shape a student's academic record. Thus, ultimately, their opportunities after graduation. This is not
273 insinuating that teachers are unfair. It means that the system itself is more complex and personal than it
274 appears on paper.

275 Future research in this topic could explore how grading practices differ across counties, or how
276 anonymous grading might reduce bias. Understanding the dynamics regarding teacher-student
277 relationships could help schools design grading systems that are both academically accurate while being
278 equitable. That would aid in ensuring that transcripts, and the college decisions tied to them, reflect
279 student learning as clearly and fairly as possible.

280

281 **Acknowledgements:**

282 We want to say thank you to all the teachers who took the time to fill out our survey. We also want to
283 thank my mentor, Elizabeth Trepainer, for helping with this study. Thank you for being a part of this!

284

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333 **Figures and Figure Captions:**

High levels of positive student engagement inherently make it easier to recognize and award partial credit on subjective assignments.

17 responses

334
335 **Figure 1.** Teachers agree that high student engagement makes it easier to give credit. (N=17) Most of
336 them said that when students are really engaged it is easier to give them credit when they do not do
337 everything right. Survey conducted through Google Forms; chart generated using Google Form's tools.
338

Strong positive rapport with a student makes it easier to understand their academic intent, even if their final exam answer is unclear.

16 responses

339
340 **Figure 2.** Teachers think that having a relationship with students helps them understand what the students
341 are trying to say even if their answers are not clear. (N=16). The numbers show what they said about
342 whether having a relationship with students helps them understand the students work. Survey conducted
343 through Google Forms; chart generated using Google Form's tools.

Students who actively participate and show enthusiasm in class generally receive higher participation marks than quiet students with equal academic output.

17 responses

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345 **Figure 3.** Teachers have ideas about whether students who participate a lot in class get better grades than
346 students who are quiet but do just as good of work. (N=17). The numbers show what they said about
347 whether students who participate a lot get grades. Survey conducted through Google Forms; chart
348 generated using Google Form's tools.

349

When a student routinely works hard and maintains a positive attitude, I am more inclined to offer them grace or extra credit opportunities at the end of a grading period.

17 responses

350

351 **Figure 4.** Teachers think about whether to give credit to students who work hard and have a good
352 attitude. (N=17). The numbers show what they said about whether they give credit to students who work
353 hard and have a good attitude. Survey conducted through Google Forms; chart generated using Google
354 Form's tools.

355

It is challenging to completely separate a student's daily classroom behavior and attitude from the evaluation of their subjective work (e.g., essays, projects).

17 responses

356

357 **Figure 5.** Teachers find it hard to separate how a student behaves from how they grade the students work
 358 (N=17).The numbers show what they said about whether they can separate a students behavior from their
 359 grades. Survey conducted through Google Forms; chart generated using Google Form’s tools.

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364 **Tables and Table Captions:**

365 **Table 1. Percent Distribution of Teacher Responses for Each Likert-Scale Question (N=16–17)**

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	No Effect
Do engaged students get credit?	0%	0%	5.9%	58.8%	29.4%	0%
Does a good relationship help understand student intent?	12.5%	6.3%	12.5%	43.8%	18.8%	6.3%
Do participating students get grades?	11.8%	23.5%	17.6%	23.5%	23.5%	11.8%

Do hardworking students get extra credit?	0%	11.8%	17.6%	52.9%	17.6%	0%
Is it hard to separate behavior from grades?	5.9%	58.8%	5.9%	29.4%	0%	0%

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Table 2. Themes Identified in Open-Ended Teacher Responses

Theme	Description	Example Quote (Paraphrased)
What students know vs what they do	Teachers separate what students know from how they behave.	“Knowing what they know is the goal. How they behave is part of the process.”
Knowing students helps	Teachers get to know students to understand their struggles.	“When I know a student well I can tell why they are struggling.”
Grading	Teachers use special tools to grade fairly.	“I use a code so I do not see the students name when I grade.”
Good attitude helps	A students attitude can affect how the teacher feels about them.	“When a student is respectful I want to help them ”
Outside pressures	Things outside the classroom can affect how teachers grade.	“Some parents can be very pushy. That can affect how I grade.”

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Table 3. What Subjects Surveyed Teachers Teach

Subject Area	Number of Teachers
Math	4
Science	3
English	6

Social Studies 3

Electives 1

Total 17

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Appendix:

376 1: High levels of positive student engagement inherently make it easier to recognize and award partial
377 credit on subjective assignments.

378 - Strongly disagree

379 - Disagree

380 - Neutral

381 - Agree

382 - Strongly Agree

383 - No Effect

384 2: Strong positive rapport with a student makes it easier to understand their academic intent, even if their
385 final exam answer is unclear.

386 - Strongly disagree

387 - Disagree

388 - Neutral

389 - Agree

390 - Strongly Agree

391 - No Effect

392 3: Strong positive rapport with a student makes it easier to understand their academic intent, even if their
393 final exam answer is unclear.

394 - Strongly disagree

395 - Disagree

396 - Neutral

397 - Agree

398 - Strongly Agree

399 - No Effect

400 4: When a student routinely works hard and maintains a positive attitude, I am more inclined to offer them
401 grace or extra credit opportunities at the end of a grading period.

402 - Strongly disagree

403 - Disagree

404 - Neutral

405 - Agree

406 - Strongly Agree

407 - No Effect

408 5: It is challenging to completely separate a student's daily classroom behavior and attitude from the
409 evaluation of their subjective work (e.g., essays, projects).

410 - Strongly disagree

411 - Disagree

412 - Neutral

413 - Agree

414 - Strongly Agree

415 - No Effect

416 6: How would you describe the difference between a student's "academic mastery of the content" vs. their
417 "classroom engagement"?

418 7: In what ways, if at all, do you feel that having a "positive relationship" with a student affects the way
419 you consider their difficulty with an assignment? (Please explain)

420 8: What type of rubrics or strategies do you have in place to make sure you are grading of a student's
421 work remains completely unbiased? (If you have none, then please explain why)

422 9: Could you please describe a specific example of a situation in which a student's positive attitude
423 positively affected a teacher's assessment of their actual subject knowledge?

424 10: What systemic pressures (e.g., school culture, parental expectations, administrative policies) make it
425 difficult to separate student-teacher relationships from final grades?

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